

Supplementary material for:

Identification of new riboswitches and ribozymes: a multiplicity of approaches and challenges

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In a previous study, we published a new method for *de novo* noncoding RNA (ncRNA) discovery where we presented a motif (28-methyl), found upstream of an RNA methylase coding gene (*mnmC*), as a potential new functional ncRNA (refer to (Naghdi *et al.*, 2017)). Our approach is based on analysing intergenic sequences upstream of genes functionally related; we use RiboGap database to access easily the intergenic sequences and GraphClust pipeline (Heyne *et al.*, 2012) to analyse rapidly our data sets. We characterized 28-methyl motif *in vitro* with inline probing assays and, using this same method, we had tested with different ligands the possibility for the motif to be a riboswitch. Following the experiment, we had no evidence for the motif 28-methyl being a riboswitch. In fact, no differences in gel migration pattern have been noticed in presence or absence of any of the ligands that have been tested. 28-methyl motif is characterized by three stems and internal and external loops with a highly conserved region (Figure S1A). Considering the resemblance of the motif with a tRNA structure, we analyzed MnmC methylase substrates. tRNA-lysine is methylated by MnmC at the wobble position (U34) (Figure S1B) (Moukadiri *et al.*, 2014), by comparing the sequences of 28-methyl motif and tRNA-Lys, we have noticed a presence of common nucleotides at approximately the same distance in both structures (Figure S1A). With this observation, we hypothesized that motif 28-methyl might mimic a structure of a tRNA to regulate *mnmC* gene expression. However, further *in vivo* analysis using a vector with *lacZ* reporter gene showed an unexpected result (unpublished data). The motif (cloned upstream of *lacZ*) and *lacZ* were under the control of lac promoter inducible with IPTG (Isopropyl β -D-1-thiogalactopyranoside). Surprisingly, the presence or absence of IPTG in the media did not make a difference. In fact, *lacZ* was expressed in both cases. Thus, we hypothesized that 28-methyl might contain a promoter region. To confirm our hypothesis, we analyzed 28-methyl sequence with BPRM (*prediction of bacterial promoters*) (Solovyev *et al.*, 2011) which predicted a promoter region overlapping the motif. Thus, for further studies using our method for ncRNA discovery, we recommend using promoter predicting tool such as BPRM to prevent selecting motifs overlapping promoters (Figure S2).

Figure S1. Apparent (spurious) similarity between putative ncRNA methyl-28 and tRNA. A) Motif 28-methyl contains a highly conserved region with some common nucleotide with tRNA-Lysine. B) *Escherichia coli* tRNA-Lysine secondary structure. Similar regions are boxed with dotted red lines. Note the different orientation of molecules according to 5' and 3' ends.

Figure S2. Updated *de novo* ncRNA discovery pipeline.

Adapted from (Naghdi *et al.*, 2017).

Table S1. Ribozyme assays with different cations

	gene	Cleave during trx	Full length	Mg ²⁺	Mn ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Zn ²⁺	Cd ²⁺	Ca ²⁺	Ba ²⁺	Cu ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Fe ²⁺	K ⁺	NH ₄ ⁺	Na ⁺
Bcep 176	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-			-	-	-		
100	Mo	+	-/+	-	-	-	-	-								
102	Zn	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-					
104	Zn	-	+	-	-				-	-	-	-	-			
106	NH ₄	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
112	Ca	-	+	-	-	-	-	-								
115	Fe	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
117	Fe	+	-/+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-			
123	Cu	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-				
125	Zn	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-				
130	-	+	-/-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		-	-	-
133	Cu	+	-/+	+/-	+/-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
135	M	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
137	Cu	-	+	-	-				-			-				

Except for Bcep176 described in the main text, the ribozyme number is the first primer number used to prepare the template of the corresponding putative ribozyme as shown in Table S2. Column “gene” corresponds to the type of metal ion to which the closest adjacent gene had an association (e.g. ribozyme 102 is found in *Branchiostoma floridae* in an intron of a Zn-finger protein), “M” refers to undefined “metal”, “-” refers to no particular metal ion. “Cleave during trx”: the ribozymes with a “+” in that column cleaved during transcription, those with a “-” did not (and could those be isolated in their *cis*-cleaving version for further tests. “Full length”: a “-” in that column ,means that the full length RNA could not be isolated (because of efficient self-cleavage), a “+” means that a full length molecule could readily be isolated and a red “+” means that the full length RNA could be isolated following cleavage inhibition by addition of high concentration of a complementary oligonucleotide (or could not be isolated in the case of “-”). The following columns indicate results (“+”, cleavage; “-” no cleavage) in presence of the corresponding ions (typically at 1 mM), empty space either means the ion was not assayed or that results were inconclusive (e.g. because of RNA degradation).

Table S2. Oligonucleotides used to prepare the ribozyme templates

	Oligo name	Genetic context	Oligonucleotide sequence
100	JP100_ABEF-Mo-F	Overlap cds	TAATACGACTCACTATAggcccgtggtggggggcccaaacagcagcactgacg
	JP101_ABEF-Mo-R	"molybdopetrin metabolism prot" (env. seq)	GTATATTTGCATGAGACTGCTCGTGGCAGTTTCGGTCATTCAGACCTCGTCAGTCGTGC
102	JP102_Branchi-Zn-F	Intron Zn-finger prot. maybe Ca-dependent	TAATACGACTCACTATAggcaccgagtaacgttagtatatttcattttgca
	JP103_Branchi-Zn-R	(<i>Branchiostoma floridae</i>)	TCTTCTGCAGACGTTTCGGTGACTGTCTGTACAC TTCATCAGTGCAAAATGAAATATAC
104	JP104_Branchi2-Zn-F	Idem 102	TAATACGACTCACTATAggagtatatttcattttgcaactgatgaaggtgac
	JP105_Branchi2-Zn-R		AACCTCTTTTATCTTCTGCAGACGTTTCGGTGACTGTCTGTACCTTCATC
106	JP106_meta-mar-NH4-F	Overlap opposite strand NH ₄ ⁺ transporter (env. Seq)	TAATACGACTCACTATAggaaaaaacccccgggtgcctcgaccgggggttcaa
	JP107_meta-mar-NH4-R		CTTACCCCGACTTCGCCTCTGCCGTAACGAAAGGCTCCTCAGGGATCTTGAACCC
112	JP112_Branchi5-Ca-F	Downstream of EGF-like, membrane prot. requiring Ca ²⁺	TAATACGACTCACTATAggggggtgggggtggttaacggcacggttggtgactg
	JP113_Branchi5-Ca-R	(<i>Branchiostoma floridae</i>)	atacgtgctaagtgaccggaacattgaattgttct
	JP114_Branchi5-Ca-R2		AAACAGAGACTTACTTCCGGACGTTTCGAGTGACATCCATCACTCTTCTTCAGGGTCACTAGAATGGACTGGCAGAACAATTCAATGTTCCGCAACAGAGACTTACTTCCGGACG
115	JP115_Desulfo-Fe-F	Downstream of Fe-dependent repressor	TAATACGACTCACTATAggcgtgtgacgacctgacttgcaaacggcccc
	JP116_Desulfo-Fe-R	(<i>Desulfovibrio vulgaris</i> prophage context)	atgccccggc TTCCTTCGGCTGCTCGTCAAGCCGGAGCCGCCACGCTCCGACGACCCGCCGCATGGGGG
117	JP117_Desulfo2-Fe-F	Idem 115	TAATACGACTCACTATAggcacgaagtagaagcgtagcgaaacggcccc
	JP118_Desulfo2-Fe-R		catgcccc TGTTCCGGCTGCTCGTCAAGCCGGCGGCCACCCGGGACGACCCGCCCGCATGGGGGG
123	JP123_Bce-Cu-F	Close to copper export protein (<i>Bacillus cereus</i>)	TAATACGACTCACTATAggcctatttttcagtgtcgaaacagtttaagct
	JP124_Bce-Cu-R		gttcaatag ATTAAATGACCTATTTCTTTCAGCAATAGGGAGGTATCTCTTATGACAGCTTAAACTG
125	JP125_Tribo-Zn-F	Close to ATPase that requires Zn, similar to pyridoxal kinase	TAATACGACTCACTATAggaaccggctctgctggttgctccatgagtgtcctg
	JP126_Tribo-Zn-R	(<i>Tribolium castaneum</i>)	gcttctacaaaatttcttttcgaaaactattagaggc
	JP127_Tribo-Zn-R2		GACCCGTTTCGCCCTTGTGGGGCTCATCAGTGCAGCGCAGTCTGCGAATGTCATGGCCCTAATA GACCCGTTTCGCCCTTGTGGGGC
130	JP130_Branchi6-F	Overlap cds	TAATACGACTCACTATAGgaagttcttttaggtacaaccaggagacttac
	JP131_Branchi6-R	"molybdopetrin metabolism prot", FolK FolB	ttccaacgtttcggttagcagcagaatcgtatccagccattctac
	JP132_Branchi6-R2	(<i>Branchiostoma floridae</i>)	AGGGTTCATTAAGCACACCAGGACTTACTTCCAACGTTTCGGTGTCTGTCAGACACCATCATCAGGGTAGAATGGCTGGATACGATTTCTGAGGGTTCATTAAGCACACCAGG
133	JP133_Ldr2-Cu-F	Adjacent Cu oxidase	TAATACGACTCACTATAggaatcaagcataactgatgagcctgggtagttc
	JP134_Ldr2-Cu-R	(<i>Legionella drancourtii</i> probable prophage)	aggcgaac GTTAGGGAACAGGATGGCTTAGCATAAGACCTTAATAAGGTTTCGCCTGAACTACCC
135	JP135_Aba-metal-F	Metal-dependent prot	TAATACGACTCACTATAggaagcataagcgaaacacaggcattcgtgctg
	JP136_Aba-metal-R	(<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> probably in prophage)	tgtctact TCTCCCTATCGTGTCTCATCAGTACTGGATCACGACATCCAGTAGACACAGGCACGAATG
137	JP137_Spr-Cu-F	Adjacent Cu homeostasis	TAATACGACTCACTATAggccgatgagcgtctggtgtttaccaaggcctg
	JP138_Spr-Cu-R	(<i>Serratia proteamaculans</i>)	agcgccg AGCCGTTATGATCGTTTCGCCGCCAGATTTCCGGCTCATCATCGGCGCTCAGGCCTTTG

Bases in uppercase of forward primers correspond to T7 promoter. Sequences are taken from (Perreault et al. 2011).

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